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The Impact of Micro-Financing in Poverty Alleviation in Sheikan Locality, North Kordofan State, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

The current study was conducted in Sheikan Locality, North Kordofan State, Sudan during 2025 aiming at assessing the impact of microfinance in poverty alleviation. A structured questionnaire based on a simple random sampling technique was used to collect data from four banks providing microfinance services in the state. A total of 368 beneficiaries were interviewed. Data were analyzed via descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests to examine relationships among variables and to test the study hypotheses. The findings revealed that microfinance had a statistically significant positive impact on poverty reduction. About 82.1% of respondents reported that project returns contributed to increasing their household income, while 66.6% indicated that they were able to acquire new assets through project revenues. In addition, 87.5% of respondents stated that microfinance had improved the quality of household nutrition. Demographic results further showed that women represented a slightly higher proportion of beneficiaries (51.9%), highlighting the important role of women in economic activities. The Chi-Square (χ^2) test results showed statistically significant relationship between microfinance returns and the main study variables. The first hypothesis confirmed a significant positive relationship between project returns and household income ($\chi^2 = 1075.9$, $p = 0.000$). The second hypothesis also showed a significant relationship between microfinance returns and improvement in health conditions ($\chi^2 = 1921.0$, $p = 0.000$). Likewise, the third hypothesis confirmed a significant relationship between project returns and educational improvement ($\chi^2 = 2686.0$, $p = 0.000$). The study concluded that microfinance is an effective instrument for poverty alleviation and socio-economic empowerment in Sheikan Locality. Its impact extended beyond increasing household income to include improvements in nutrition, health, education, and asset ownership. The study therefore recommended expanding microfinance services, simplifying access procedures, and strengthening training and technical support for beneficiaries in order to ensure the sustainability of small enterprises and maximize their developmental impact.

Keywords: microfinance, poverty, Sheikan Locality, North Kordofan state, Sudan

INTRODUCTION

Microfinance widely developed and expanded in recent decades globally and gained international interest, owing to its proven efficiency in combating poverty and unemployment while fostering the growth and development of small-sized enterprises in various countries. This achieved by making financing accessible to the poor and low-income individuals, who constitute a crucial client base for microfinance institutions. Many countries, including Sudan, have established several financial institutions offering microfinance services to clients who have demonstrated their capability to repay these loans. Through these small-sized enterprises, employment opportunities created, and production is enhancing, thereby the competitiveness of small business sector increased.

Microfinance has emerged as an important policy instrument for poverty alleviation by providing financial services to low-income households excluded from formal banking systems. These services include small loans, savings, insurance, and other financial products designed to support income-

generating activities and enhance household welfare. Microfinance institutions (MFIs) have emerged as crucial players in the global effort to alleviate poverty and stimulate economic development. The significance of microfinance lies in its potential to address the poverty as one of the most pressing global challenges and offering diverse services to pursue the economic empowerment of marginalized populations. Traditional financial institutions often overlook low-income individuals due to perceived risks and high transaction costs. MFIs fill this gap by adopting innovative lending practices and leveraging social collateral, which makes financial services accessible to those who were typically excluded from the formal banking sector. By doing so, microfinance not only enhances financial inclusion but also fosters a sense of entrepreneurship and self-reliance among the poor. In addition to poverty reduction, microfinance had been credited with promoting broader economic development. The infusion of capital into underserved communities can lead to job creation, increased productivity, and economic diversification. Furthermore, the positive externalities associated with microfinance, such as improved education and health outcomes, contribute to the overall development of societies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept and Importance of Microfinance:

Microfinance refers to the provision of small-scale financial services, including credit, savings, and other financial products, to low-income individuals who are excluded from formal banking systems. It aims to support income-generating activities, promote self-employment, and improve the living standards of economically disadvantaged groups. According to Hamid and Jibril (2010), microfinance is a financial or in-kind facility designed to empower low-income and economically active individuals to engage in productive activities.

Microfinance is also viewed as a form of social innovation that addresses societal needs through non-traditional financial mechanisms. As noted by Phills (2009), social innovation refers to novel solutions to social problems that create value for society as a whole rather than for private individuals. In this context, microfinance has gained increasing attention from governments and development organizations as a tool for supporting small enterprises and vulnerable groups.

Historical Evolution of Microfinance:

The origins of modern microfinance can be traced to the 1970s with pioneering institutions such as the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh and the SEWA in India. These institutions demonstrated that providing small loans to the poor, particularly women, could enhance income generation and empowerment.

Over time, microfinance evolved into a global development strategy focused primarily on poverty reduction. Microfinance institutions (MFIs) expanded their services beyond credit to include savings, insurance, and financial training, becoming key actors in financial inclusion and poverty alleviation in developing countries.

Microfinance and Poverty Alleviation:

Poverty remains one of the most persistent global development challenges. Although global poverty rates have declined over time, Sub-Saharan Africa continues to record the highest incidence of poverty. The World Bank (2010) estimated that a significant proportion of the population in the region still lives below the international poverty line. In countries such as Nigeria, poverty is strongly associated with rural underdevelopment, limited access to financial services, poor infrastructure, food insecurity, and low agricultural productivity. One of the major constraints facing the poor is limited access to formal credit, which restricts their ability to engage in productive economic activities and escape poverty.

Concept of Poverty

Poverty is commonly defined as a condition of deprivation in basic consumption needs such as food, clothing, and shelter (Ravallion & Badani, 1994). It may also be understood as a lack of capabilities that prevents individuals from participating fully and with dignity in society (Aluko, 1975). According to World Bank there are three forms of poverty: Absolute poverty, Relative poverty and Social exclusion poverty.

Poverty is therefore multidimensional and influenced by limited access to key resources such as education, land, infrastructure, social networks, and financial capital. Effective poverty reduction strategies must address these structural constraints.

STUDY AREA AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study area:

North Kordofan State lies between latitudes 12°:00–16°:30 N and longitudes 27°:00–32°:25 E and includes Sheikan, Bara, Um Ruwaba, and El Rahad localities. The state is characterized by clear ecological and climatic variation, ranging from desert conditions in the north with annual rainfall of less than 100 mm, to semi-desert and semi-arid conditions in the south with rainfall ranging between 100–400 mm. This variation has resulted in diverse soil types, including sandy soil (Goz), which is widely cultivated despite its low fertility due to its easy tillage and is mainly used for millet, groundnuts, sesame, watermelon, and Roselle. It also includes fine-textured soils such as gardud, jurraba, and wadi soils, which are suitable for sorghum, sesame, and vegetables, as well as scattered clay soils particularly in El Rahad area that are suitable for mechanized agriculture. This environmental diversity has also led to variations in vegetation

The population of the state is estimated at about 2.9 million according to the 2009 census, with around 80% living in rural areas. Administratively, the state is divided into twelve localities. The majority of the population depends on a traditional livelihood system based on rain-fed agriculture and livestock rearing, alongside the presence of nomadic pastoralists, including cattle herders (Baggara) in the south and camel herders (Abbala) in the north, who move seasonally in search of pasture and water. The main crops include millet as a staple food, sorghum as a secondary crop, and groundnuts, sesame, and gum Arabic as major cash crops, in addition to limited production of vegetables and horticultural crops near urban areas. Livestock production plays a crucial role in the local economy, with camels concentrated in the north, cattle in the south, and sheep and goats distributed across the region, contributing significantly to household income, food security, and social activities.

The economic structure of North Kordofan is largely based on traditional rain-fed farming and animal husbandry, with supplementary income from forestry products such as gum Arabic and charcoal.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a mixed methodological approach focusing on data collection and analytical techniques. Primary data were collected through a structured household questionnaire administered to selected households within the study area. The collected data were then analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to achieve the study objectives. The main tool of analysis was descriptive statistics, which were used to summarize and organize the data in a clear and meaningful way. These included measures of central tendency such as mean, median, and mode; measures of dispersion such as range, variance, and standard deviation; frequency distributions expressed in counts and percentages; and position measures such as percentiles and quartiles. These statistical techniques helped in describing socio-economic characteristics such as age, gender, education level, household size, income, and expenditure patterns, and provided a base for identifying patterns and trends within the data (Kaur et al., 2018; Field, 2018). In addition, the Chi-Square (χ^2) test, a non-parametric statistical tool, was used to examine the relationship and association between categorical variables. This test evaluates whether there is a significant difference between observed and expected frequencies under the assumption of independence, and is particularly useful for analyzing nominal and ordinal data (Agresti, 2018). The Chi-Square test was applied to assess relationships such as the association between socio-economic characteristics of households and adoption of agricultural practices, as well as other categorical variables relevant to the study. The test is mathematically expressed as $\chi^2 = \sum(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$, where O_i represents observed frequencies and E_i represents expected frequencies. Overall, the combination of descriptive statistics and Chi-Square analysis provided a comprehensive framework for interpreting the data and drawing meaningful conclusions from the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Household Demographic Characteristics:

The results of the study show that respondents' demographic characteristics, including sex, age, marital status, educational level, family size, occupation, and income, play an important role in influencing economic activities and livelihood patterns within the study area. The findings indicate that more than half of the respondents were female (51.9%), while males accounted for (48.1%), suggesting that women play a significant role in economic activities. Regarding age distribution,

47.8% of respondents were within the age group of 41–50 years, 28.8% were aged 30–40 years, and 17.9% were above 50 years, indicating that microfinance services are mainly accessed by mature and economically active individuals capable of managing income-generating activities. In terms of education, 14.7% of respondents had basic education, 31.0% had secondary education, and 54.0% had university education, reflecting a relatively high level of educational attainment. The marital status results showed that the majority of respondents were married (70.1%), while 16.6% were single, 6.0% were divorced, and 7.3% were widowed, which suggests that married individuals form the dominant group, possibly due to their greater financial responsibility and commitment to loan utilization and repayment. The average household size was 5 persons with a standard deviation of 1.4, indicating moderate variation among households. With regard to occupation, 28.0% of respondents were employees, 4.9% workers, 30.4% self-employed, 31.0% farmers, and 5.7% livestock breeders, showing a diversified livelihood structure. Finally, the average household income was SDG 253,000 with a standard deviation of 16.3, reflecting noticeable variation in income levels among the surveyed households. (Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5).

Figure (1): Frequency distribution according to gender

Figure (2): Frequency distribution according to age

Figure (3): Frequency distribution according to educational level

Figure (4): Frequency distribution according to marital status

Table (5): Frequency distribution according to job

Contribution of project revenues to increase income, increasing ownership of new assets and improving the quality of nutrition:

The results of the study showed that project revenues had a positive impact on the economic and living conditions of the majority of respondents. Regarding income improvement, 82.1% of the respondents reported that project revenues helped increase their incomes, while 17.9% stated that there was no improvement in their income. In terms of asset accumulation, 66.6% of the targeted individuals indicated that project revenues enabled them to acquire new assets, whereas 33.4% reported no contribution in this regard. Furthermore, the findings reveal that 87.5% of respondents stated that project revenues contributed to improving the quality of their nutrition, while 12.5% reported no improvement. Overall, these results indicated that project revenues have played a significant role in enhancing income levels, improving asset ownership, and strengthening household nutrition among the majority of beneficiaries. (Figure 5, 6, 7).

Figure (6): Contribution of project revenues to increasing income

Figure (7): Contribution of project revenues to increasing ownership of new assets

Figure (3): Contribution of project revenues to improving the quality of nutrition

Discussion of the Hypotheses:

The discussion of the hypotheses showed that the first hypothesis is strongly supported by the results, where 77.2% of respondents agreed and 16.0% strongly agreed with its statements, while only 6.6% did not agree. The relative importance was 81.8%, indicating a high level of agreement. The Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 1075.9$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.000$) showed statistically significant differences in responses, and the median value of 4 confirmed overall agreement, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis and confirming a significant relationship between microfinance returns and income levels. Similarly, the second hypothesis results revealed that 67.4% of respondents agreed, 22.0% strongly agreed, 8.8% were neutral, and 1.8% disagreed, with a mean score of 4.10 and relative importance of 82.0%, indicating a positive perception of the impact of microfinance on health. The Chi-square result ($\chi^2 = 1868.3$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.000$) confirmed significant differences among responses, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative, which confirms a statistically significant relationship between microfinance returns and health improvement. In the third hypothesis, 83.3% agreed and 7.2% strongly agreed, while 7.6% were neutral and 1.6% disagreed, with a mean of 3.96 and relative importance of 79.2%, indicating strong agreement on the educational impact of microfinance. The Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 2686$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.000$) also confirmed significant differences among responses, leading to acceptance of the hypothesis and confirming that microfinance returns significantly improve educational outcomes by supporting school attendance, covering educational costs, and reducing dropout rates (Tables 1, 2, 3).

Table (1): relationship between the returns of microfinance projects and the level of income

Items	Frequency	Percent %
Strongly Agree	296	16.0
Agree	1422	77.2
Neutral	0	0.0
Disagree	122	6.6
Strongly disagree	0	0.0
Total	1840	100.0
Mean	Relative Importance	Degree of Importance
4.9	81.8%	high
(χ^2)	(df)	(p-value)
1075.9	2	0.000

Table (2): relationship between the returns of microfinance projects and the health level

Items	Frequency	Percent %
Strongly Agree	404	22.0
Agree	1241	67.4
Neutral	161	8.8
Disagree	34	1.8
Total	1840	100.0
Mean	Relative Importance	Degree of Importance
4.10	82.0	high
(χ^2)	(df)	(p-value)
1921	3	0.000

Table (3): relationship between the returns of microfinance projects and the educational level

Items	Frequency	Percent %
Strongly Agree	107	7.2
Agree	1227	83.3
Neutral	113	7.6
Disagree	25	1.6
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	1472	100.0
Mean	Relative Importance	Degree of Importance
3.96	79.2	high
(χ^2)	(df)	(p-value)
2686	3	0.000

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined the impact of microfinance on poverty reduction in Sheikan Locality, North Kordofan State, by analyzing its role in improving income levels, enhancing asset ownership, and improving the living conditions of beneficiary households. The findings revealed that microfinance is an effective tool in supporting the economic activities of low-income households, as it significantly contributed to increasing the income of the majority of respondents. It also helped beneficiaries acquire new assets and improve the quality of nutrition. Moreover, the results indicated a clear positive impact of microfinance on both health and education aspects, reflecting its broader contribution to improving overall quality of life. The statistical analysis, particularly the Chi-square tests, confirmed the existence of significant relationships between microfinance returns and income, health, and education variables, thereby supporting the study hypotheses. Accordingly, microfinance can be considered an important instrument for poverty alleviation and for promoting economic and social empowerment in the study area. In light of these findings, the study recommends expanding microfinance services, simplifying access procedures, and strengthening training and technical support programs for beneficiaries to ensure the sustainability of small-scale projects and to achieve greater developmental impact within the local community.

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